

TRANSMISSION AND GATHERING OF DATA EFFICIENTLY IN WIRELESS SENSORS NETWORKS

Anuja Choudhary
C.S.E.

MERI College of Engineering and Technology, Sampla, Haryana

ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: For routing in WSNs there are several routing algorithms are proposed and PEGASIS is one of the most important routing algorithm among all of them as it is base algorithm for all the other approaches. These all the approaches are the chain based hierarchical approaches and have been proposed in order to provide a network of better lifetime and the load balancing energy consumption in the network. IEEPB's improved version IIEEPB is proposed with the removal of long links, selection of leader optimally and improvement of load balance energy consumption.

Findings: We have proposed an improvement in our work in order to solve the load balancing and long link removal by keeping the threshold of the node degree and distance of the node from the other node. A new method is also considered while selecting a leader and then a new method of the data transmission is also adopted to decrease the delay in the data transfer.

Also, a new improvement for the Modified-PEGASIS is also proposed as an improvement for the PEGASIS. It has a new method to chain construction and leader selection but the data transmission is still the same as in the PEGASIS. We have proposed a new method for the modified-PEGASIS too which has efficient chain construction method and reconstruction method by adopting a new method for collecting and data transmission.

Methodology: We have used MATLABR2010a to illustrate that both the proposal proposed1 and proposed2 works better than IIEEPB and modified-PEGASIS respectively.

Keywords: Wireless, Sensors, Networks, PEGASIS, Modified-PEGASIS, Routing, Algorithm, IIEEPB

1.0 INTRODUCTION

With the development and advancement of technology production of sensor devices that can perform various tasks like sense thing, compute and process and communicate become quite easy and can be produce on large scale without any interruption and problem. People all around the world are conducting several types of research on wireless devices over the past several years and so far those researches have made our life easier. As we can see everything around us has some kind of sensor in them as they had made everything very easy to use, so they should be available at

cheaper rate, in smaller size and with long life too and it is important to develop such sensors with efficient hardware as well software solutions.

Sensors are generally very small device so they are equipped with small parts i.e. like small battery. We do not use recharging battery with the sensors because of the deployment constraints, so we need to design the routing protocols very carefully in such a way that we can make use of the limited resources like battery, computation and storage very efficiently. These limitations are probably going to stay, since most of the time it is likely to misuse innovative upgrades to create littler and more vitality productive gadgets as opposed to making them all the more powerful. WSNs are used in different applications in different ways which leads to the requirement of the different network requirements and communications algorithms or we can say patterns.

If we need to use the WSN for a particular application we need to organize sensors in area which needs observation, detecting of required criteria (like temperature, weight, dampness and so on.), correspondence of detected information to the sink utilizing some directing convention and handling information and send desired data to the client. In most of the cases i.e. applications sensors are deployed randomly that is there is no fixed pattern where as in some of the applications we require the definite routing algorithm. In WSNs routing of the data is very important as maximum amount of energy is wasted while transmitting data from one place to another. So we need a routing algorithm through which can utilize the limited amount of energy or battery to give the maximum possible lifetime of network i.e. we require an algorithm which makes sensors to dissipate the equal amount of energy after given period of time.

As we can see with the rapid advancement of the technology the use of Wireless Sensor Network is increasing day by day and they are becoming more and more popular. Various places where we see the use of wireless sensor network are Driverless Cars, Smart homes and City, Smart Waste Management and Automated leakage detection system, Traffic and Pollution monitoring, Fire and Radiation detection etc. These some applications mentioned showed how the use of wireless sensor network has made our life easier and how they are becoming popular day by day. Figure given below is showing how the use of the sensor networks we are going to build of smart cities in future.

2. Abbreviations and Acronyms

PEGASIS: Power Efficient Gathering in Information Systems

WSN: Wireless Sensor Network

LEACH: Low Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchy

EPPB: Energy Efficient PEGASIS Based

IEPPB: Improved Energy Efficient PEGASIS Based

CREEC: Chain Routing with Even Energy Consumption

IBCA: Intersection Based Coverage Algorithm

PBCA: Phase Based Coverage Algorithm

RFND: Round of First Node Death

RMND: Round of Middle Node Death

RLND: Round of Last Node Death

PDCH: PEGASIS with Double Cluster Head

PEDAP: Power Efficient Data Gathering and Aggregation

PEDAP-PA: Power Efficient Data Gathering and Aggregation Power Aware

M-PEGASIS: Modified Power Efficient Gathering in Information System

DFS: Depth First Search

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

In the recent years we have that everything around us is turning smart whether it is television, city, home, vehicle, healthcare or manufacturing process etc. everything is going is under change i.e. smart change that means everything is nowadays we used consists of sensors and their networks. In the past few years, so many researches had been conducted on WSNs through which we came to know about the strength and weaknesses of the WSNs. It has been seen that recently researchers are working on overcoming those limitations and minimizing the effect of those limitations on the use of sensors.

As we know some of the limitations of sensors like limited amount of energy, computing capacity or memory they lead to several challenges regarding the design of the network, routing and collection of data too. There is need to develop new routing protocols for the WSNs to maximize their life span.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

To determine the how strong and reliable our wireless sensor network is depends on the lifetime of the Wireless sensor networks. There are several protocol suggested earlier to determine the lifetime of a wireless sensor network and how to improve it like LEACH, PEGASIS and Modified PEGASIS that helps in increasing the lifetime of the WSNs but not in efficient. Routing is considered as the most important part of the whole activity. If someone uses the hierarchical architecture then they have two options i.e. Cluster based and chain based routing technique. If someone uses the chain based routing technique then they have two options in it too. First one is use a chain that has branches i.e. chain is formed with connectivity degree more than one and other one is to form chain with connectivity degree of one i.e. forming a chain that has no branches. While designing or considering any of the routing techniques there are several factors which may need to be consider like energy consumption, scalability i.e. to check how scalable our technique is is going to be, connectivity, is it fault tolerant or not, is it mobile or not etc.

Reason behind using the routing approach is:

- Maximizing network lifetime
- Balanced energy consumption
- Time delay

There are lot of routing known to us and have been proposed till date with an objective either increasing the lifetime of a network or how to maintain the balanced energy consumption or both. All there protocols are characterized on the basis of the techniques they used to do i.e. whether they do it by the nature of the network or according the structure of a network or data forwarding techniques. They are listed below:

- Data centric protocols
- Hierarchical protocols
- Location based protocols
- QoS aware protocols

The class which classified the protocols on the basis of their structure is Hierarchical protocols. The most important protocols that come under the hierarchical protocols are APTEEN, LEACH, PEGASIS and TEEN. They are further classified as follows:

- Cluster based
- Chain based

Cluster based consists of LEACH, TL-LEACH, EECA, EEUC, etc. whereas the Chain based consists of PEGASIS, EEPB, IEEPB, CREEC etc. Some of the protocols allow the chain branch in the chain based hierarchical protocol while some don't. PEGASIS, ANT-PEGASIS and CREEC follow the simple chain protocols while the others follow the branched chain like EEPB, IEEPB etc.

- **PEGASIS:** It is also known as the Power Efficient Gathering protocol which was proposed by the Cauligi S. Raghavendra and Stephanie Lmdsey for the sensor information system. This protocol follow the greedy approach with the hierarchical chain based routing protocols. It was proposed in 2001. In this protocol they have considered some presumptions which are as follows:
 - Base station is situated at a far location from the sensing area and considered to be stationary while being monitored.
 - They are considered to be homogeneous by nature i.e. they have same capabilities at the initial level.
 - All nodes are immobile.
 - All sensors are deployed in the random manner over the area only.
- **PEDAP and PDAP-AP:** These two approaches were proposed in 2003 by Tan, üseyinÖzgür, and Ibrahim Körpeoğlu for the hierarchical chain bases networks which are totally based on the PEGASIS protocols and also using the concepts of minimum spanning

tree. Unlikely PEGASIS it works in two phases only first is chain formation and second phase is data transmission phase there is no leader selection in this approach as all the data is transmitted along the spanning tree edges. In this approach Base Station is considered as the root of the tree. It mainly focuses on forming an optimal chain and it works fine in rounds too.

- **EEPB:** This improved version of PEGASIS was proposed by WEI Gang and YU Yong-Chang. It is somewhat similar to the PEGASIS in the approach it uses but it is round based. In it every round consists of three major phases same as PEGASIS i.e. chain construction or formation, leader selection and the last step is data transfer but the difference lies in the chain construction and leader selection phase of this approach otherwise data transmission phase is similar to the PEGASIS. It uses the threshold approach in order to avoid the formation of long links in the chain construction phase. For selection of leader it uses the distance of node from the Base Station and energy remaining in that node as the important parameter. Rate at which the leader is selected varies or dependent on the number of the nodes alive in the network. It overcomes or we can say removed some of the problems of the PEGASIS but still not able to give us a perfect approach as it has some of its limitations too.
- **Modified-PEGASIS:** As the name suggests this is the modified version of the PEGASIS with the lot of improvements like modified method used for the formation of the chain and leader selection too. This method was proposed by Madhuri Gupta and Laxmi Saraswat. In this approach branched construction method is used by keeping the distance and ID of the node as the important parameter. If a node which is already present in the network and there is a recently added node which is nearest to that node, then if the old node has ID greater than the recently added one then it can be added to the chain by connecting that node the recently added one. This approach also unable to makes sure that the long link never forms as the end node has an option if it wanted to connect with chain or not. In the next phase for selecting leader sensor the parameters that used are remaining energy of the node, its degree and its distance for the base station. If a node have maximum remaining energy, least distance from the base station and least degree as well then it is selected as the leader of the chain. This approach works better than the PEGASIS if we consider the lifetime of the network but still the load balanced energy consumption still persists. Data is transmitted in the similar fashion as it did in PEGASIS.

4. RESEARCH GAPS OR NEED OF THE STUDY OR MOTIVATION FOR THE STUDY

There is always a room for improvement in every technical field even in wireless sensor networks routing. New methods can be used to construct chain that no longer form long chains and new leader selection method can be used. Data transmission can also be change in order to increase lifespan of the network.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

From the previous chapter we have collected lot of information about the different routing protocols and techniques used by them but still there is a long way to go, lot of things left out for the researchers. Last chapter give us details like energy efficiency, load balancing and time delays needs to be calculated optimally in order to give perfect routing protocol. We got to know that transferring data with the optimal use of energy and minimum time delay is the main concern of the wireless sensor network because of the limited energy they have. Among several hierarchical nature routing architectures PEGASIS and LEACH are the most important one. LEACH used cluster based approach while PEGASIS uses chain based approach. PEGASIS is considered as more energy efficient as compared to LEACH as in PEGASIS only one packet is sent and received by the node during one round whereas in LEACH multiple packet send and received by a node at a time. This makes PEGASIS more energy efficient and load balanced too.

PEGASIS stands for Power Efficient Gathering of Sensor Information System. This architecture have three steps one is chain formation or chain construction, next is leader selection and last one is data transmission. Although it has several advantages but it has some loophole too like problem of long link formation. As it uses the greedy approach to form chain this leads to non-optimal chain length. Also, the low load balancing leads to leader selection in a non-optimal manner and the data transmission takes place with the large time delay and are considered as some of the major problem of the PEGASIS.

After the PEGASIS proposed several other protocol came or developed by the researchers like PEDAP and PEDAP-PA, EEPB, IEEPB, PEGASIS-IBCA, PEGASIS-PBCA, PEG-ANT, MH-PEGASIS, COSEN, CREEC, MH-PEGASIS, PDCH, MODIFIED-PEGASIS, and MULTI-CHAIN PEGASIS etc. They were proposed with a sole goal of making WSNs work efficiently. Each uses different techniques to improve the different phases of the PEGASIS but still there is no vast development and they still suffer just like PEGASIS do.

After considering the above routing protocols we are going to proposed two new techniques which might work as an improvement to the existing one. First proposal, proposal1 used the IEEPB as the base approach and uses the modified algorithm in order to improve the performance of the system. This works in the similar fashion as the PEGASIS did like the three phases chain formation, leader selection, and data transmission with some little modification which enhances the load balancing and network lifetime. It considers threshold of degree of a node and connectivity degree as the main parameters. Second proposal is Proposal2 which uses Modified-PEGASIS as the main base protocol to enhance the network lifetime and improving the problem caused by the long links formation. It uses the connected component approach to deal with the long links problem. This will help in improving the performance of the system. It also helps in reducing the time delay while

transmitting the data. It follows the same pattern as Modified-PEGASIS uses like chain formation, leader selection and data transmission. But after the first phase second phase include the removal of long link removal then come the leader selection then data transmission.

Here, first we are going to explain the system model we used and the assumptions made for these new approached we are going to propose. After that we will analyse the performance of the work proposed.

5.1 System Model

Here the system model is described which consists of the network and energy model as well for the work proposed. Environment of the network and capabilities of the sensor nodes is described in the network model and the energy model is used to describe how the energy consumption takes place while one sensor node communicate with the other nodes.

5.1.1 Network model

Network model consists of the N number of nodes and one base station. Nodes are spread over a square area of A x A while the sensor node is located a fixed location with coordinates (X, Y) that may lie within or outside the range of the network. The sensor nodes do their usual work of sensing the network and the send the sensed data to the base station and the base station as always is ready to receive data from the sensor nodes or the leader node and then present the condition in which the sensor are sending the data to the user. Given below are the characteristics of the network model:

- Nodes are deployed randomly over the network area.
- Sensors are immobile.
- All sensors know about the base station location, their own ID and energy levels.
- All sensors have the same features like same energy level, processing power etc.
- Base station is located at a far and fixed location from the sensing area.
- All nodes can communicate with the base station directly.

5.1.2 Energy Model

Fig 5.1: First Order Radio Energy Model

It can be seen from the above radio model that it contains one amplifier, one power amplifier and one receiver. The energy is dissipated when the transmitter and receiver works i.e. when data is transmitted. There are two propagation models:

- Free-space propagation model.
- Two-ray ground propagation model.

In free space model of propagation there is single path or we can say direct line is there in between the transmitter and the receiver while in the other model i.e. two-ray ground model of propagation does not have any direct contact line between the transmitter and the receiver. It used the electromagnetic waves which bounce back from the ground and then transmitted to the receiver using different paths and time duration.

The propagation loss of energy in the free space propagation model is inversely related to the d^2 where d is the distance between the receiver and the transmitter whereas in two-ray ground model of propagation it is inversely proportional to the d^4 . Here, we are using the amplifier in order to amplify the power used for transmission so that energy lost during the propagation can be compensated.

Thus, energy dissipated while transferring data at distance d of K bits is equals to

$$E_{Trans}(k, d) = k * E_{elect} + k * \epsilon_{fs} * d^2, d < d_0$$

$$k * E_{elect} + k * \epsilon_{amp} * d^4, d \geq d_0 \quad (5.1)$$

Free space model is used when the propagation distance d_0 small or very less otherwise the two-ray ground model is used.

While receiving k-bits of data energy dissipated is equals to:

$$E_{rx}(k) = k \times E_{elect} \quad (5.2)$$

And the energy used or dissipated while the data is fused is equals to:

$$E_{df}(k) = k \times E_{da} \quad (5.3)$$

Where,

E_{elect} : Energy consumed while transmitting 1-bit data.

ϵ_{fs} : Energy of amplifier in free space model of propagation

ϵ_{amp} : Energy of amplifier in two-way ground model of propagation.

E_{da} : Unit energy possessed by the aggregated data.

d_o : Threshold distance which can calculated by:

$$d_o = \sqrt{\epsilon_{fs} / \epsilon_{amp}} \quad (5.4)$$

5.2 Proposed Work

The main focus we have while proposing this work is to provide an approach that gives less time delay, have load balanced energy consumption for chain based routing on WSNs. Also, it focuses on delaying the death of the first node i.e. increasing the lifetime of the network. Here we are proposing two approaches.

Improved version of EEPB is IEEPB which also works on PEGASIS methods with some changes so that it can overcome the limitations of the EEPB and the PEGASIS routing approach. Similarly, modified version on the PEGASIS named Modified-PEGASIS is the enhanced version but still suffers from few problems from which the PEGASIS suffers. Problem statement 1 is based on the IEEPB improvement while Problem statement 2 is the improved version of Modified-PEGASIS.

5.2.1 Problem Statement 1

It states the building an aware system for the development of energy so that load balanced protocol can be maintained by keeping time delay minimum in a homogeneous WSNs. This will helps in improving the lifetime of the network, help in forming an efficient chain and finding leader optimally.

Solution for the problem is given by the following method:

5.2.2 Proposed solution: Proposed 1

This part is about the solution for the problem mentioned above. It works in the same three phases i.e. chain construction, leader selection and data transmission. Description of all the phases is given below:

Fig 5.2: Different Phases in a round and working of protocol.

5.2.2.1 Construction of chain

This phase of our approach is same as it is in IEEPB with the addition of Threshold of Node Degree which needs to take in the account while considering the distance between the nodes or while connecting one node to the other. It is the first parameter we have added in our research. Benefit of using this parameter that bound the maximum degree a node can have or the maximum connecting capacity of the nodes with the other nodes. Steps involved are:

- a) Store the IDS of all the nodes that are alive. After that make the degree of connectivity of these nodes to zero. Proceeding moves forward only for the alive nodes.
- b) Find the node which is at the maximum distance from the base station from that group of alive nodes. Set the farthest node as the first node of the chain.
- c) Now the node which is recently added to the chain find a node which is at the minimum distance from it and also not a part of the chain. Make that i^{th} node as next node and add it to the chain.
- d) After that search for the node that has connectivity degree less than T_{nd} from the remaining $i-1$ nodes. Let the number of left nodes with that degree is m . So is $m \leq i-1$.
- e) After that, i node search for the other j node with same qualification i.e. nearest to it and not a part of the chain. After finding join i by j and increase degree of both i and j by 1.

$$j = \min(\text{distance}(i, k)) \text{ where } 1 \leq k \leq m. \quad (5.5)$$

$$\text{node_degree}(i) = \text{node_degree}(i) + 1 \quad (5.6)$$

$$\text{node_degree}(j) = \text{node_degree}(j) + 1 \quad (5.7)$$

f) Now, repeat step (c) to (e) till the entire alive node gets connected to be the part of the chain.

This will lead to the formation of a chain with following properties:

$\text{Node_degree}(i) < T_{nd}$ where $1 \leq i \leq \text{number of nodes in the chain}$.

Fig 5.3: Construction of Chain

Above figure shows us how the chain is formed after using the mentioned approach. ID of every node is represented by a number. Red node with ID87 is the starting node of the chain and the green node with the ID20 is the last node of the chain. Every node has degree less than T_{nd} this will help in maintaining the load balance energy consumption while fusing and receiving the nodes.

5.2.2.2 Selection of Leader

Next phase of this approach is selecting a leader. Selection of leader depends on several parameters like node degree, initial and residual energy of the node and also, the distance of the node from the

base station. Following steps involved in it are as follows:

- Node which has the highest remaining energy can resist the communication costs to the base station as it has enough energy and it won't die in the middle of the on-going process.
- Decrement rate of energy is a great way of knowing the node capability as it helps in finding how quickly is the node dying.
- Selection of leader is done according to the following equation:

$$LEADER = \max (W (i)) \quad (5.8)$$

$$W (i) = (RE/E_o) \times (1/Node_deg (i)) \times (1/D_{toBS} (i)) \quad (5.9)$$

Where the i^{th} has following properties:

RE is remaining energy of the node

E_o initial energy of that node

$Node_deg$ degree of the node

D_{toBS} distance of a node from the base station

5.2.2.3 Data transmission

As we are following the IEEPB as the base approach for our proposal1 which also follows the same data transmission technique as used by the EEPB and the PEGASIS routing protocol which is the single token based approach for transferring data from one node to other and for receiving too but we are proposing here different approach for transferring data from node to other and also for receiving the data in which different token is used for both process. Leader will possess two types of tokens one is FTOKEN and other is CTOKEN. FTOKEN is used for transmitting data while CTOKEN is used for collecting data to all the nodes which are taking part in such processes. Leader initially transfers the CTOKEN to the nodes which are connected it directly and FTOKEN to all the nodes which have fused data from all the other nodes that starts from the neighbour of the leader. All the sub nodes used this same approach for transmitting and receiving data from the sub chains which are originating from them.

In the figure 5.3, let's assume node with ID92 is the leader node and it sends the CTOKEN to the nodes with ID31, ID91 and ID8. Now these nodes send CTOKEN to the nodes which are the part of their sub chain like node with ID8 send CTOKEN to the nodes with the ID5 and ID48 and this process kept on repeating until are completed. Now, the node with ID8 wants to receive the data so it sends the FTOKEN to the node with the ID5 and after receiving from node with ID5 it sends the FTOKEN to node with ID48. After receiving data from both the nodes it fuses the data. Now node with ID8 waits until it gets the FTOKEN from the leader node which is ID92. Leader

node uses TDMA to transfer the FTOKEN. After receiving the FTOKEN from the leader node all the nodes one by one send the data to the leader node. As soon as the leader node receives the data from all the nodes it fuses all the data and transmits it to the base station. This shows that a node can occupy multiple CTOKEN but only can have FTOKEN in order to receive data which prevents collision of data packets.

From this approach we can say time delay during the whole process is directly proportional to the length of the sub chain.

$$TimeDelay_{new} \propto \max(\text{length of sub-chain originating at LEADER}) \quad (5.10)$$

But in IEEPB it used the only one token for transmitting data which leads to time delay to directly proportional to total length of the chain.

$$TimeDelay_{ieepb} \propto \text{Total length of the chain} \quad (5.11)$$

It shows that the approach we proposed here works significantly and help in reducing the time delay while transmitting the data.

5.2.3 Problem Statement 2

Second problem is to develop routing protocols for homogeneous WSNs is that help in forming a chain based routing protocols that avoids the formation of the long links and reduction of the time delay while transmitting the data.

5.2.4 Proposed solution: Proposed 2

This part is about solving the problem mentioned above. This solution also works in the three phases i.e. construction of chain, leader selection and transmitting data. It used the Modified-PEGASIS as the base approach i.e. chain formation is done in the similar fashion as it does in Modified-PEGASIS but with the improvement that will help in removing the long links formed during chain formation. So here chain formation takes places in several sub-phases:

1. Forming a chain using the Modified-PEGASIS technique.
2. Removal of long links formed during the process using the concept of DFS connected component. This phase is known as chain reconstruction.

Fig 5.4: Different phases and working of proposed 2.

5.2.4.1 Chain formation

This approach also uses the same technique as used by IEEPC and EEPB for the formation of the chain initially. It considers the ID number of the node and its distance from the base station as important parameters. A node can connect to the node which is previously visited node but it should be the nearest distance from that node that is going to join it. It takes place in following steps:

- a) Node with the ID1 is given the first chance to connect with the nearest neighbour of its. From this step chain formation starts.
- b) Next step is to connect with node which is nearest to that node and its node ID is greater than the node which it is going to join.
- c) Repeat step (b) until all the nodes get connected to form a chain. There will be no loops formed during this process.
- d) After the chain start growing, start the search for the nodes that causes the long links formation and the last node which has node to get connected with it. But there is very less probability to find such nodes as there are N-1 nodes remaining and there might be a possibility that any one is connected to that last node.

5.2.4.2 Chain reconstruction

Form the above chain formation method chain is formed easily but it contains several long links which leads to formation of chain which has long length. This in return increases the dissipation energy of the sensor and the network as well. This phase removes the long links formed during chain formation step using the concept of connected component of DFS. Steps for the process are given below:

Fig 5.5: Chain formation using Modified PEGASIS having long links

- a) Calculate the threshold distance and the length of the chain as well.

$$T_d = \frac{\text{Total length of all links}}{\text{number of alive nodes}} \quad (5.12)$$

- b) Links whose length is greater than T_d are considered as long links. Now delete all the long links which in return forms a network having some disconnected components and some connected ones.

- c) Try connecting these components using the minimum distance criterion i.e. minimum distance form any sensor node, or from any component etc. Steps for this process are:

1. Select a disconnected component from all the disconnected ones.
2. From the selected components nodes find a node which is nearest to it and not a part of that component.
3. In next step find a sensor pair which is at the minimum distance form pairs.

4. Connect sensors that give us a big component that is now connected.
5. Repeat step (2) to (5) for the component formed until they form a chain of connected components shown in figure 5.7

Fig 5.6: Disconnected chain after removal of long links.

Fig 5.7: Chain formed after reconstruction.

Following the above procedure helps in forming a chain which don't have a long link chain and length of chain is also reduced. This will help in reducing the energy consumed in the network while communicating. Now a leader is selected after the data is transmitted from the base station.

5.2.4.3 Leader Selection

Using the same criterion i.e. energy remaining the node, its initial energy, its degree and distance from the base station and equation (5.8) and (5.9) a leader node is selected. For every sensor node W is calculated and the node with the minimum value of W is selected as leader. Now as always leader will coordinate the data transmission between the nodes and the base station.

5.2.4.4 Data Transmission

Like the Modified PEGASIS and PEGASIS have the same approach which they used for transmitting data from one node to other we are also using the approach we used in proposal1 for the data transmission. We are going to use two token FTOKEN and CTOKEN which is different from PEGASIS one TOKEN approach. FTOKEN used to transmit data to parent node while CTOKEN is used to tell children that be ready for data transmission.

6. Future Scope and Conclusion

This research is devoted to the problem that occurs while forming a chain or selecting a leader in a chain in WSNs with the goal of improving the load balanced energy consumption and increasing network lifetime of the sensor nodes and the network as well. To find a better solution we have drawn inspiration from the works and researches conducted on this topic earlier.

In our research, we had proposed two different approached which follows the basic outlines of the PEGASIS protocol in order to determine a better solution for a chain based hierarchical WSNs. Result of both the proposed approaches are compared with the previous researches by using the same simulation tool and under the same environment for the simulation too. Result and analysis shows that both of the proposed approaches works better than the previous ones. Also, our proposed approaches are able to increase the network lifetime, improve the load balanced energy consumption and reduce the time delay while transmitting the data significantly.

Even we can see that our proposed protocols have given the improvement for the previous protocols in every parameter field i.e. whether it is for chain formation, leader selection, time delay, increasing lifetime etc. but still there is room for improvement which can never be close. This modification is just or could be the introduction of the improvement in quality of service management, data collection and transmission in a secure way, time delay reduction and time critical application etc.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Lindsey, and C. Raghavendra, "PEGASIS : Power-efficient gathering in sensor information systems" IEEE Aerospace Conference Proceedings, 2002, pp.1125-1130.
- [2] Tan, Hüseyin Özgür, and Ibrahim Körpeoğlu. "Power efficient data gathering and aggregation in wireless sensor networks." ACM Sigmod Record 32.4 (2003): 66-71.
- [3] W. R. Heinzelman, A. Chandrakasan, and H. Balakrishnan, "Energyefficient communication protocol for wireless microsensor network," in 33rd Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences,,2000, pp. 3005 – 3014.
- [4] R. G. Gallager, P. A. Humblet, and P. M. Spira, "A distributed algorithm for minimum-weight spanning trees," ACM Transactions on Programming Languages and Systems, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 66–77, January 1983.
- [5] YU Yong-chang, WEI Gang, "An Improved PEGASIS Algorithm in Wireless Sensor Network," Acta Electronica Sinica, vol.36, pp.1309-1313, July 2008.
- [6] Sen, Feng, Qi Bing, and Tang Liangrui. "An improved energy-efficient pegasis-based protocol in wireless sensor networks." Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge Discovery (FSKD), 2011 Eighth International Conference On. Vol. 4. IEEE, 2011.
- [7] Linping, Wang, et al. "Improved algorithm of PEGASIS protocol introducing double cluster heads in wireless sensor network." Computer, Mechatronics, Control and Electronic Engineering (CMCE), 2010 International Conference on. Vol. 1. IEEE, 2010.
- [8] Han Jingjing, Xu Zhongwei. CCLP algorithm,for improving current PEGASIS protocol. Information Technology,2008,10:55-58
- [9] GUO Wen-yu, ZHANG Wei, and LU Gang, "PEGASIS protocol in wireless sensor network based on an improved ant colony algorithm," Second International Workshop on Education Technology and Computer Science, 2010, pp.64-67.
- [10] Young-Long Chen, Neng-Chung Wang, Chin-Ling Chen and Yu-Cheng Lin, " A Coverage Algorithm to Improve the Performance of PEGASIS in Wireless Sensor Networks," 12th ACIS International Conference on Software Engineering, Artificial Intelligence, Networking and Parallel/Distributed Computing, 2011, pp.123-127.
- [11] Young-Long Chen, Yu-Cheng Lin and Neng-Chung Wang, "an intersection-based coverage algorithm for pegasis architecture in wireless sensor networks," Proceedings of the 2012 International Conference on Machine Learning and Cybernetics, Xian, 15-17 July, 2012, pp.1727-1731.
- [12] Wang, Xiaorui, et al. "Integrated coverage and connectivity configuration in wireless sensor networks." Proceedings of the 1st international conference on Embedded networked sensor systems. ACM, 2003.
- [13] Xing, Guoliang, et al. "Integrated coverage and connectivity configuration for energy conservation in sensor networks." ACM Transactions on Sensor Networks (TOSN) 1.1 (2005): 36-72.
- [14] Zibouda Aliouat and Makhlof Aliouat, " Efficient Management of Energy Budget for PEGASIS Routing Protocol," 6th International Conference on Sciences of Electronics, Technologies of Information and Telecommunications (SETIT), 2012, pp.516-521.
- [15] Mohsin Raza Jafri, Nadeem Javaid, Akmal Javaid and Zahoor Ali Khan, " Maximizing the Lifetime of Multi-Chain PEGASIS Using Sink Mobility," World Applied Sciences Journal 21, 2013, pp.1283-1289.
- [16] Liang, Weifa, Jun Luo, and Xu Xu. "Prolonging network lifetime via a controlled mobile sink in wireless sensor networks." Global Telecommunications Conference (GLOBECOM 2010), 2010 IEEE. IEEE, 2010.
- [17] Liang, Weifa, Jun Luo, and Xu Xu. "Prolonging network lifetime via a controlled mobile sink in

- wireless sensor networks.*" Global Telecommunications Conference (GLOBECOM 2010), 2010 IEEE. IEEE, 2010.
- [18] Nakayama, Hidehisa, et al. "A novel scheme for WSN sink mobility based on clustering and set packing techniques." *Automatic Control, IEEE Transactions on* 56.10 (2011): 2381-2389.
- [19] Luo, Jun, and Jean-Pierre Hubaux. "Joint sink mobility and routing to maximize the lifetime of wireless sensor networks: the case of constrained mobility." *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking (TON)* 18.3 (2010): 871-884.
- [20] Gupta, Madhu, and Laxmi Saraswat. "Energy aware data collection in wireless sensor network using chain based PEGASIS." *Recent Advances and Innovations in Engineering (ICRAIE)*, 2014. IEEE, 2014.
- [21] Shin, Jisoo, and Changjin Sun. "CREEC: Chain routing with even energy consumption." *Communications and Networks, Journal of* 13.1 (2011): 17-25.
- [22] Bazzi, Hiba Sami, Ali Masoud Haidar, and Ahmad Bilal. "Classification of routing protocols in wireless sensor network." *Computer Vision and Image Analysis Applications (ICCVIA)*, 2015 International Conference on. IEEE, 2015.
- [23] El-Aaasser, Minar, and Mohamed Ashour. "Energy aware classification for wireless sensor networks routing." *Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT)*, 2013 15th International Conference on. IEEE, 2013.
- [24] Sharma, Mukesh. "Wireless sensor networks: Routing protocols and security issues." *Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)*, 2014 International Conference on. IEEE, 2014.
- [25] Lewis, Franck L. "Wireless sensor networks." *Smart environments: technologies, protocols, and applications* (2004): 11-46.
- [26] Loscri, V., G. Morabito, and S. Marano. "A two-levels hierarchy for low-energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (TL-LEACH)." *IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference*. Vol. 62. No. 3. IEEE; 1999, 2005.
- [27] Wang, Zijian, Eyuphan Bulut, and Boleslaw K. Szymanski. "Energy efficient collision aware multipath routing for wireless sensor networks." *2009 IEEE International Conference on Communications*. IEEE, 2009.
- [28] Li, Chengfa, et al. "An energy-efficient unequal clustering mechanism for wireless sensor networks." *IEEE International Conference on Mobile Adhoc and Sensor Systems Conference*, 2005.. IEEE, 2005.
- [29] Akyildiz, Ian F., et al. "Wireless sensor networks: a survey." *Computer networks* 38.4 (2002): 393-422.
- [30] Akkaya, Kemal, and Mohamed Younis. "A survey on routing protocols for wireless sensor networks." *Ad hoc networks* 3.3 (2005): 325-349.